

OPERAS

open scholarly communication in the european
research area for social sciences and humanities

Supporting European capacities for Social Sciences and Humanities academic publishing and scholarly communication:

The role of OPERAS research infrastructure

**OPERAS Community: Policy Brief
December 2023**

Executive summary

The European Commission has been supporting Open Science for many years, both at a political level with official documents and a financial level with infrastructure funding and the building of the EOSC. Most recently are the Council Conclusions on Research Assessment and Implementation of Open Science, which emphasises the role of Open Access publishing as a core component of Open Science.

OPERAS was identified in the Conclusions as one of the major organisations able to support the “European approach and capacities for academic publishing and scholarly communication”.

Open Science goal is a more sound and transparent science, which can be a game changer in the achievement of the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Hence, research should not only be responsive to societal needs but co-created in deep dialogue with society itself.

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure dedicated to open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities. OPERAS plays a key role in the Open Science policy as it:

- ▶ focuses on “open scholarly communication”, thus directly enabling this dialogue with society and, within the ESFRI landscape, positioning OPERAS at the convergence of different axes (namely, FAIR data and publications), with a higher capacity to engage with other infrastructures for a fully functional European Research Infrastructure ecosystem, as envisioned in the EU Commission documents
- ▶ is a distributed infrastructure, OPERAS is the catalyst in sharing knowledge and know-how, in the adoption of practices to increase the quality, efficiency and return on economic and cultural investments both on the sides of the service providers and the content creators
- ▶ is supported by an International Non-profit Association under Belgian Law (AISBL) built upon strong principles that are keys for OPERAS governance and community management, based on the UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science and the POSI (Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructures) principles

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- ▶ creates synergy at any level, as it clearly results from the active membership in EOSC Association, from the signature and the active involvement in the COARA initiative for the reform of research assessment by pooling its services, and from the active role played since the beginning in the drafting and implementation of the Diamond Open Access plan for an equitable, community led and community driven Open Access publishing
 - ▶ is supported by an active and engaged network of 12 national nodes, recognising and respecting the value of diversity and integration.

This in turn means that OPERAS:

- 1.** increases the quality, visibility and impact of research in the Humanities and Social Sciences by providing relevant and community-based open scholarly communication services
- 2.** is one of the main pan-European actors to support high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing
- 3.** promotes diversity of languages, formats, cultures, publishing and linguistic practices. As an infrastructure with a robust range of services, OPERAS is a sanctuary to boost multilingualism, publishing diversity (i.e bibliodiversity), and scholarly inclusion
- 4.** in its capacity building boosts the transition to Open Access for academic imprints, it supports Open Access publishers that actively practise equitable models
- 5.** is the only European RI gathering all the diversity of scientific actors: publishers, service providers, data analysts, librarians, researchers, and engaged stakeholders from civil society. OPERAS federates the different stakeholders and leverages their contribution towards reaching the goal of ethical and open publishing.

Introduction

As the Conclusions of the Council on Research Assessment and Implementation of Open Science emphasises, European citizens and the European economy must be able to contribute to and benefit from a shared research knowledge system. Today, there is a strong and urgent need to improve, adapt, or even build a regulatory framework that enables access to publicly funded research results, and their re-use. Most preoccupying is the rise of expenditures related to access to scientific publications and scholarly communication at large. These expenditures affect the resources of both research institutions and member states. Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) disciplines are extremely diverse, arguably more diverse than STEM (science, technology, engineering and maths) disciplines, and they are linguistically dispersed while SSH research units tend to be relatively small, and focused on very specific topics. Also, SSH are not as international as STEM, although they are universal as the methodology is concerned: they are mainly dealing with matters related to the home country of the institution/researcher, including their national languages. Therefore international collaborations are harder (and more rare). Moreover, the impact of SSH research on societies is less obvious than is the case with many STEM areas of research. It is less easily integrated in economic models of development and, being multilingual, it may remain largely invisible to communities that do not practise more than their own language plus English. Yet this impact remains major and requires help to be sustained. And it can be vastly improved if communication issues among SSH practitioners – for example possibilities of translations – can be addressed as a whole and collaboratively. However their scholarly communication practices face very common issues that can be addressed as a whole and in a collaborative manner.

OPERAS is a European Research Infrastructure for the development of open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities. OPERAS provides European researchers a single access point to a wide range of scholarly communication and publishing services offered by its members and thus ensure that scholarly community gets the most out of SSH that these sciences can contribute to open science. OPERAS supports efficient and sustainable publishing services across Europe by coordinating the different actors (university and scholar-led presses, libraries, dissemination platforms and other services providers).

OPERAS' mission is to innovate and support open scholarly communication for Social Sciences and Humanities in the European Research Area by coordinating and federating resources, communities and practices in Europe and beyond.

OPERAS' vision is to make Open Science a reality for SSH research and achieve a scholarly communication system where knowledge produced in the SSH benefits researchers, academics, students and, more generally, addresses societal challenges and supports society to reach sustainable development goals.

OPERAS plays a key role in the Open Science policy: it focuses on “open scholarly communication”. From its SSH perspective, OPERAS can bring an original form of expertise to Open Science, and especially Open Access. OPERAS catalogue of services has been conceived to increase the impact of the whole SSH domain and thus address scientific and societal challenges. From this perspective, OPERAS Research Infrastructure highlights the role and strength of SSH in science at large.

▶ OPERAS positioning in the European policy framework

The Open Science policy

The Conclusions of the Council on Research Assessment and Implementation of Open Science clearly insist on the need to better support Open Access publishing and open scholarly communication from both a financial and a strategic perspective. To increase the impact of science, and especially its use and reuse by different stakeholders, open scholarly communication practices must be shared and improved in a coordinated manner. This coordination should be managed at the political level by the Member States, and also at the scientific level by increased collaborations between scientific organisations: defining priorities, gaps; supporting Open Access publishers; developing innovative practices of scholarly communication, increasing the visibility and access of the scientific outputs, etc. This list, coming from the Council Conclusions, shows how Open Access is an asset in the Open Science policy and the need to have a Research Infrastructure dedicated to it.

As mentioned in the document, this work must consider the challenges related to the different disciplines. However, the SSH are highlighted for this purpose because of their specific scholarly communication practices and their important use of national languages.

THE COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION [...] WELCOMES the setting up of [...] dedicated research infrastructures such as [...] OPERAS (Open scholarly communication in the European Research Area for social sciences and humanities);

(Council Conclusions on Research Assessment and Implementation of Open Science, p. 9)

The European Research Infrastructures policy

Collaboration is also addressed in the context of the European policy on Research Infrastructures (RI), especially “for the advancement of science, science diplomacy, tackling global challenges and increasing access to excellence” as written in the Council Conclusions on Research Infrastructures published in December 2022. In this perspective, it is particularly welcome to engage with Research Infrastructures that have close relations or that are part of the same scientific domain. The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) has developed a dedicated taxonomy for Research Infrastructures based on their specialties and socio-economics impacts. The Social and Cultural Innovation (SCI) domain, for instance, deals with Research Infrastructures that are related to Social Sciences and Humanities.

Different Research Infrastructures have been identified as contributing to the SCI domain as highlighted in the schema below, taken from the Landscape Analysis part of the ESFRI roadmap 2021 (p. 79).

The schema shows the complementarity between the different Research Infrastructures in the SCI domain. It highlights that OPERAS operates on a different axis, one that tackles the challenges of SSH as a whole while focusing on scholarly communication. In doing so, OPERAS’ capacity to engage with the SCI infrastructures is higher and can cover different aspects of both the Open Science policy (data, FAIR, research assessment, etc.) and the Research Infrastructures policy (EU missions, societal challenges, etc.).

The recent Council Conclusions on Research Infrastructures have called for a “fully functional and operational European RI ecosystem, which efficiently integrates European, national, as well as regional RIs of various sizes [...] to provide with knowledge-based solutions to grand societal challenges, to support overall EU priorities and contributes to prosperity and well-being in Europe.”

At the crossroads of these two policy frameworks is the building of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), one of the most important implementations of the Open Science policy where the contribution of Research Infrastructures is highly expected. The Council Conclusions on Research Infrastructures recognise “a key role of ESFRI and thematic RIs working together with EOSC core developers and operators to speed up the implementation of open science policy and the FAIR data management, and to promote interdisciplinary R&I in Europe.”

▶ OPERAS in the European Social Sciences and Humanities Open Access publishing context

OPERAS fosters the co-creation and adoption of scholarly communication services addressing SSH researchers' needs in terms of discovery, content creation, quality assurance, dissemination, outreach, and evaluation of research outputs. As a distributed infrastructure, OPERAS is the catalyst in sharing knowledge and know-how, in the adoption of practices to increase the quality, efficiency and return on economic and cultural investments both on the sides of the service providers and the content creators.

OPERAS RI is supported by an International Non-profit Association under Belgian Law (AISBL). It is built upon strong principles that are keys for OPERAS governance and community management and based on:

1. UNESCO Recommendations on Open Science 2021 (incl. infrastructures)
2. the principles of open scholarly infrastructures

Empowering Social Sciences and Humanities research by collaboration

OPERAS RI has engaged into several collaborations on different levels with the SSH ESFRIs. Three different tools structure the general framework of collaborations between OPERAS and the SSH ESFRIs:

- ▶ Signature of Memoranda of Understanding: with the SSHOC community in May 2022 and with CESSDA in September 2022.
- ▶ Opening a seat at the General Assembly level through dedicated supporting membership with DARIAH.
- ▶ Being partners in different EU projects for the SSH community (OPERAS-P, TRIPLE, OPERAS-PLUS, SSHOC, Palomera). Most of these projects are initiated by OPERAS to call for collaboration with the existing ERICs from the Social and Cultural Innovation domain.
- ▶ Being part of the SSHOC governing board to address in an aligned way the SSH needs.

OPERAS added values

- ▶ OPERAS Research Infrastructure is a member of the EOSC Association and as such it has joined the operational group made of the ESFRIs that are members of the Association.
- ▶ In collaboration with Science Europe, Coalition S and ANR, it published the Diamond Action Plan and will be the provider of the future capacity centre for Diamond Journals.
- ▶ OPERAS has been identified as one of the primary organisations able to support the “European approach and capacities for academic publishing and scholarly communication” in the Council Conclusions on Research Assessment and Implementation of Open Science.
- ▶ OPERAS has signed the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA) call on research assessment and supports the Coalition through some of its services.

Based on the above, OPERAS Research Infrastructure adds value in different ways:

Added value 1:

OPERAS increases the quality, visibility and impact of research in both Humanities and Social Sciences by providing relevant and community-based open scholarly communication services.

OPERAS has the potential to be a crucial part of European RI landscape. It is strongly integrated very well with existing ERICs and it is aiming to play a crucial role in providing scholarly communication services for SSH at the European level and to provide them through a one-stop platform. Hence, the argument that there is a gap in the SSH infrastructure that OPERAS can fill with respect to scholarly communication is justified. Especially the question of open access and monographs is crucial.

Quote from the reviewers of the OPERAS ESFRI Application, 2021

Added value 2:

OPERAS is one of the main pan-European actors to support high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing.

HIGHLIGHTS the importance of non-profit, scholarly open access publishing models that do not charge fees to authors and where any author can publish their work without funding/institutional eligibility criteria; NOTES the variety of models that do not depend on article processing charges (APC); (Council Conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing, p.5)

Added value 3:

OPERAS promotes diversity of languages, formats, cultures, publishing practices, linguistic practices. As an infrastructure with a robust range of services, OPERAS is a sanctuary to boost multilingualism, publishing diversity (i.e bibliodiversity), and scholarly inclusion.

ACKNOWLEDGES that publishing practices vary across disciplines, and EMPHASISES that some publication formats, such as monographs, books and long-text formats, especially in the humanities and social sciences, must continue to be supported, allowing for a diverse range of models to co-exist; (Draft Council Conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing, p.4)

Added value 4:

OPERAS boosts the transition to OA for academic imprints, it supports OA publishers that actively practise to OA models.

ENCOURAGES Member States and the Commission to invest in infrastructures for publishing based on open source and open standards, in order to support technological interdependency and avoid the lock-in of services, and to connect these infrastructures to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) federation; (Draft Council Conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing, p.7)

Added value 5:

OPERAS is the only European RI gathering all the diversity of scientific actors: publishers, service providers, data analysts, librarians, researchers, and engaged stakeholders from the civil society. It federates the different stakeholders and leverages their contribution towards reaching the goal of ethical and open publishing.

As ESFRI reviewers observed in their report from the OPERAS application, "OPERAS provides a unique and key part of the scholarly communications landscape".

Sustaining OPERAS at the Member States level

This section is made by members of OPERAS Executive Assembly – each represents one country – to highlight in which perspective OPERAS is a must have at national level.

Portugal

Besides contributing to the Portuguese national roadmap for research infrastructures, OPERAS is particularly apt at providing services and guidance to the Portuguese Higher Education publishing landscape, helping academic presses to gain more international visibility, boosting as well Portuguese as a fully scientific language. It naturally complements the work that is being done by the national nodes of infrastructures such as DARIAH and OpenAire.

Netherlands

Because OPERAS contributes to the Dutch national roadmap for large-scale research infrastructures (2021) with services that no other infrastructure provides and because OPERAS demonstrates how its services connect to other infrastructures in ways that add value to the scholarly communication landscape, open being the default.

Italy

Because in 2020 OPERAS has been included in Italy's 'National Research Infrastructure Plan (PNIR) 2021-2027' as a high-priority research infrastructure in the Social & Cultural Innovation domain.

France

Because OPERAS is an important opportunity to achieve the objectives of the National Plan for Open Science in the humanities and social sciences. It is also a way for French infrastructures already in place (OpenEdition, Huma-Num) to extend their activities to the European level. Finally, OPERAS is a way to federate the French communities and to bring them to act on a European scale.

Slovenia

OPERAS is intended to be complementary to other infrastructure initiatives, especially in the field of scientific publishing. The main concern of the funders is that OPERAS should not overlap with older and similar infrastructures, DARIAH and CLARIN. As most of the infrastructure for science is not in the hands of SSH, it is important to raise awareness that it is only SSH that can promote open science.

Germany

OPERAS as every other RI is expected to reach out directly to research communities, pursuing very much a hands-on and direct approach, thus bridging the gap between infrastructures and researchers. Besides OPERAS should find its own specific role in the evolving landscape of the national German infrastructures (collaborating and cooperating with DARIAH, CLARIN etc. and the NFDI consortia [=national research data infrastructures] in the making).

Greece

OPERAS will enhance the visibility and capacities of institutional publishers, while helping in the promotion of Open Science in the country and the collaboration of the Greek SSH community

Poland

OPERAS allows for a successful exchange of knowledge and experiences in scholarly communication (?), both on a national and international level, between individual initiatives focused on Social Sciences and Humanities. OPERAS provides international visibility for Polish research outputs as well as services that could be used by local researchers, librarians and publishers in SSH. In particular, given the publishing landscape consisting of numerous small publishers who are mostly publicly funded, there is a need for sustainable and inclusive services that will facilitate their work on monographs.

Croatia

Croatia boasts a rich tradition of academic publishing. Currently, 500 open-access journals are produced through a shared national platform, with over 60% of them belonging to the social sciences and humanities domain. The OPERAS initiative inspires Croatian researchers to enhance the standard of scholarly publishing in Croatia. By engaging actively with the OPERAS community, we stay abreast of the latest trends and newest developments in scholarly communication and the best practices and innovation in scholarly publishing. This exchange of knowledge is mutual, and alongside the strong support of OPERAS, we contribute our expertise and unique perspective of scientific publishing from a small scholarly community that embraces openness in a particular manner

United Kingdom

Because of the Plan for OPERAS to facilitate private/public partnerships in the ERA, particularly with small commercial publishers, which is important to support the UKRI policy and support bibliodiversity – may also support the suitable publisher exception which though will effect small foreign language presses. UKRI has also implemented an open access books policy that is supported by OPERAS.

Norway:

Because OPERAS contributes to the Norwegian roadmap for international research infrastructures and supports the Norwegian policy on open science by being an RI where open is default. OPERAS as a research infrastructure will bring Norwegian SSH researchers closer to their European peers and will facilitate tools, platforms and meeting points which will bring the open Scholarly community together. OPERAS will also contribute to the strengthening of SSH research in Norway and Europe.

The Council of the European Union ACKNOWLEDGES that, beyond their fundamental missions in the areas of R&I, nationally and regionally anchored RIs act as an amplifier for regional development, when offering highly qualified jobs, including the managerial, scientific, technical, administrative and other positions, and boosting development of their sites and neighbouring regions by stimulating the development of new businesses, supply chains, civil infrastructure and related services, thereby shaping regional economic strategies. Council Conclusions on Research Infrastructures, p.4

► Conclusion

OPERAS knows and serves The SSH community. However, OPERAS' expertise in open scholarly communication practices is also transferable to other scientific domains, especially regarding the Diamond Open Access model. The shift towards Open Science is a systemic one, OPERAS RI is in a unique position to offer solutions for SSH that can be extended to STEM disciplines. In this perspective, sustaining OPERAS and its services contributes to support the Open Science policy and the Research Infrastructures policy that better address SSH Open Access publishing challenges.

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